

ASUU STRIKE AND ITS IMPLICATION ON THE UNIVERSITY SYSTEM IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Strike action by the staff of federal universities in Nigeria has been a disturbing event that has drawn the concern of every citizen. The problems of this phenomenon abound: it makes planning for universities academic activities difficult as educational managers face the challenge of re-planning educational activities, re-preparing the school calendar, re-assigning old task to new staff and not achieving certain long term goals, among others. This paper is set, therefore, to examine the implications of strike on the Nigerian University system. A brief history of strike action by the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) was analyzed and the causes were thoroughly explained; its effects on the students, lecturers, Universities and the society were also evaluated. It was observed that strike is a problem that has lingered for too long, yet nothing serious has been done to abate it. Also, managing strike requires the attention of both the government, education managers, academic staffs as well as other relevant stakeholders. The study recommends (among others) that government should improve the welfare and condition of services of lecturers and provide them with adequate infrastructural facilities in order to improve their working environment. Also, the employers and employees interpersonal relations should be enhanced and constructive communication process should also be developed in order to curb reoccurrence of strike.

Keywords: ASUU, Strike, Implication, Nigerian, University.

Introduction

Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) is a subset of the Nigerian Association of University Teachers formed in 1965. The association gained its autonomy in 1978 and began to operate as a union that fights for the rights of her members. The union is further saddled with the responsibility of assisting the stakeholders in attaining the aim of classic standard of education through the provision of quality education in the Nigerian University system. Further, the union also supports the struggle just like other unions to ensure adequate welfare for her members, job security and ensures enabling working environment for her members as it is in other nations (Monogbe, 2019).

ASSU, as a union, had five branches of Federal Universities under the direction of its first president, Dr. Biodun Jeyifor of University of Ibadan. The Universities included University of Ibadan, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, University of Ife and University of Lagos. Today, the union has Professor Victor Emmanuel Osodeke, who came on board on 30th May 2021, as its president; and he obviously came to meet the same struggles that have been lingering for a long period of time in the academic sector of the country (Monogbe, 2019).

On 22nd June 2009, the National Executive of ASUU declared a total and indefinite strike to compel the federal government to sign the agreement reached with ASUU on the re-negotiation of June, 2001. On November 2016, ASUU went on a one-week warning strike. That strike was a culmination of the persistent call on the Federal Government to address issues bothering on how to re-position the Nigerian University System based on the desire to deal with the rot and decayed in the system. The understanding was reached on the issues leading to the warning strike, but government went to sleep after the strike action was suspended. ASUU embarked on an indefinite strike on August 14, 2017 due to government failure to redeem the terms of agreement signed in 2009 and the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) endorsed by both parties in 2012. The strike lasted for over a month and was called-off on 17th September 2017 pending when the government will implement the new agreement. Areas of the new agreement included funding for revitalization of public universities and the issues of Earn Academic Allowances, the issue of the university staff schools and the implementation of the judgment of national industrial court, National Universities Pension Management Company and guidelines for pension matters for professor. All these are the strike regimes that have befallen tertiary institutions in Nigeria (Odim Annastashia, Solomon, 2018). ASUU has again embarked on another industrial action due to inability of the federal government to keep the agreement they signed since 2009. The strike action has lingered from February 14th, 2022 to 24th October 2022 and has posted so many implications on the university system and the entire society in which so many have loss their lives in the process.

The struggle since 2009 might have been caused by some disagreements between the union and the government and has generated a number of implications in the lives of student, lecturers, the university system and the entire society which has called for great concern from different agencies, organizations, individuals and the entire nation on ways of resolving the menace and allow educational sector to be functional.

Statement of the Problem

Over the years, ASUU in Nigeria has embarked on serious strike actions and the situation has become a reoccurring decimal in our tertiary educational system and mostly anchoring on the non-payment of salaries with increment and allowances. As a matter of fact, no matter the name given to the strike action that takes place, it is a situation that gives no one pleasure as strike actions by ASSU have negative impact on the students, lecturers, university and the society at large.

Students across several institutions of higher learning in Nigeria are on a regular basis being confronted with strike actions, and the disagreement or lack of understanding between government and academic staff union of universities do frequently end in gridlocks that generally disrupt and sometimes even undermine academic calendar and higher education in Nigeria.

According to kagbararen (2022), the repeated strike actions is undoubtedly decreasing the academic performance of students as a result of suspension of learning process in schools for a long period of time. The implication is that the students' reading abilities will wane. Also, the prolonged program completion and graduation, and the idle time can be so frustrating to students whose home condition may not be favorable, and many times, can leave them vulnerable to vices and easy recruits for criminal activities such as arm robbery, kidnaping and rape (Ajayi, 2013).

Education is a vital tool to the survival of any nation and as such, it should be seen and treated beyond political sentiments. It is not deniable that Nigeria is presently not doing enough by world standard in the funding of education. To that effect, this paper is geared to discuss the effects or implications of the incessant strike actions on the students, lecturers, the university and the society at large.

CAUSES OF STRIKES IN NIGERIA

It is popularly said that there is no smoke without fire. Strike does not occur in a vacuum, there is a cause behind them. The following are perceived causes of strike:

Poor and inconsistent payment of salaries

It is obvious that the university lecturers are often underpaid and most times being paid part salaries. That has made the lecturers not to be happy due to the fact that many politicians on monthly basis go home with heavy bags of money even when most of them are not educated. Amadi and Urho (2015) noted that the underpayment of university lecturers vis-a-vis their counterparts in other economic sectors and the discriminating salary structure between the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) have been a major cause of their dissatisfaction.

Poor conditions of service

Lecturers in Nigerian universities are not offered additional incentives and their working conditions are not well developed. Clear examples are those in health and other sectors who receive extra payment for hazards in their jobs, but such cannot be heard of in education even though there are also hazards in lecturing (Odim, Annastashia and Solomon, 2018). Amadi and Urho (2015) pointed out the condition of service or employment which include such features as working conditions, i.e., working environment, hours of work, over time shift work, flexible working hours, fringe benefits, i.e., sick pay, subsidized meals, pension scheme, company goods at a discount, company cars are not there. Whenever the incentives and working condition is not there, it will surmount to strike action.

Political interference in Education

Today, the autonomy of the University is nowhere to be found because it is not given the grounds to operate as an entity without the leaders in political offices trying to influence its activities. Decision making in the educational sector is not possible without the interference by the political leaders. Amadi and Urho (2015) also noted that the reasons why so many lecturers leave universities is because there is a lot of interference in academic freedom by the government.

Poor funding of the educational sector

There was an attempt by the United Nations to improve the educational system in Nigeria. They recommended that 26 percent of the Nation's budget should be channeled into the education sector. But it is quite so sad that the government, up till date, has never met such conditions, and this have led to poor funding and poor maintenance of existing plants in campuses. Amadi and Urho (2015) noted that the annual budget on education is too low compared to the budget made for other things in the country. Example, the budget for elections and numerous huge amount of money mismanaged can be considered as being responsible for the existing poor teaching and learning facilities in our universities and poor quality graduates produced.

Non-compliance of Agreement

It is always pertinent that a worker and the employer always reach an agreement after series of negotiations. But in some cases, one party may decide not to honor the agreement. For example, since December 2009, ASUU has been embarking on series of strikes following the federal government failure to honor the agreements they reached with the union.

Unnecessary Delay in Payments of Salaries and other Emoluments

The delay in payment of salaries without any justifiable reason may cause lecturers to embark on strike for such salaries to be paid. Ezeagba (2014) noted that in Nigeria, many organizations always delay or refuse to pay their workers' salaries and other emoluments even when the organizations concerned have sufficient funds to pay. Based on that, the universities in Nigeria are not exempted from it as government refuses to pay the lecturers their salaries with claims of lack of fund. This can always result in a strike action.

EFFECTS OF THE ASUU STRIKE ACTIONS

These struggles have imposed negative impacts on the students, lecturers, the university system and the economy at large. While the students are idle, some are forced to go in search of petty employment in some big organizations. And as a result of this, most of them that have secured the job or other means of generating money may not wish the strike to be called off soon, some may decide not returning to classroom as the salary they now receive is large and they are not sure of getting such jobs after school. This may cause education to lose its value and also increase rate of school dropouts in the country.

Most organizations consider age as an important aspect whenever employments are to be offered. This is a barrier for most youths in Nigeria as strike actions continue to prolong their study years in the universities. With this, there will be increase in the rate of youthful crime and insecurity because many students will be lured into illegal businesses like cyber-crime, gambling, fraudulent acts and immorality.

Ajaji (2013) also noted that the incessant strikes carried out by the ASUU have unintentionally affected the students of Nigerian universities, pointing out that it typically poses a lot of challenges to them by prolonging their program completion and graduation and that the idle time can be so frustrating to students whose home condition may not be favorable; and many times, can lead them to becoming vulnerable and easy recruits for criminal activities such as armed robbery, kidnapping and rape. This has made them a problem to the society. However, though students are thus affected, lecturers are not left out as they are directly faced with the struggle, which most times result in lack, want and even death.

Sadly, many reports of examination malpractices in government owned institutions of learning can be attributed without any doubt to the incessant strike actions that do repeatedly reoccur during academic session. This is because the longer students stay at home, the faster the process of reduction in their mental abilities and as a result, they find it difficult to recall what they were taught during the learning period.

Every child will consider it a waste of time and energy to be studying during the strike period and this will result in generating poor grades at the end of the session. Every institution that is unable to produce students with good grades, will stick on the lecturers' bad reputations and reduces their capacities academically.

Presently in Nigeria, the union is facing a court case with the federal government due to the refusal to implement the agreement that they had since February, 2009 which have negatively affected the lecturers' effective functionality. The federal government has come up with a policy of "no work no pay", which has resulted to so many unexpected incidences such as untimely death of so many lecturers due to the fact that payment of salaries has been put on a hold.

The hindering of lectures who are doing masters and PhD programs from achieving their degree on time also is a negative impact of strike action. This definitely affects the university system negatively. The fact that the educational attainment of the institution will drastically reduce is not to be over emphasized. This may be as a result of the increase in class repetition by the students which will present the institution before others as not being up to the standard of competing with a private owned universities.

Furthermore, the parents may not wait a second in relocating their wards to a private owned university. This action has inflicted a high level of poverty on parents, mostly to those who have provided the basic amenities for their children already on campus. On the other hand, the rich who can afford sending their children to the private universities where academic calendar is unaffected can generate conflict and hatred among families and will increase the rate of crime, immoralities and untimely pregnancy in a bid to compete and live up to the societal expectations.

Implications on the University System

The entire university system is always put at a hold whenever strike action sets in during an academic session. This means that all academic activities such as the managing, planning, decision making and lecturing will be disrupted. According to Igbaji (2009), strike action is as a result of two different ideologies and opposing interests between government and academic staff union of university which often result in deadlock, putting students across various institutions of higher learning in a constant state of delay and frustration. Oladipo (2012) stated that strike would result in the academic calendar being compressed and parts of the curriculum skipped, and that some topics would not be treated and the students will have to write the exams, resulting in poor performance and decline in quality of education.

It is unfortunate that government has not maintained the agreement they signed with ASUU in 2009 despite the number of strike actions. The incessant strike actions has ended up placing Nigerian educational system on a low rank in the world ranking due to these negative implications inflicted on the students and the lecturers. Adesulu (2014) noted that incessant ASUU strike negatively influence graduates of the Nigerian public university as the chance to quality teaching is negotiated during the industrial strike while most lecturers find their way into private universities where resources are made available and quality teaching is rewarded. Also, during the ASUU industrial action, most of the union members would go about doing their private businesses and upon resumption, adequate preparation is not made, as such, students are not entitled to quality education.

The academic ranking of the world universities (ARWU) is determined by several indicators such as the academic or research performance of Alumni, staff, including Nobel Prizes, Field Medals, major cited researchers and articles indexed in major citation publications and the per capita academic performance of an institution (ARWU, 2010). Ukwu (2013) stressed that the disastrous nature of the ASUU strike has not only encouraged shabby jobs among university lecturers in lecturing students, but has also contributed to the poor ranking of Nigerian tertiary institutions.

It is obvious that strike actions has built numerous negative impacts on the educational sector. The effect of the breaks in academic sessions whenever strike action sets in can be so devastating, affecting the students both psychologically and socially, and delaying the lecturers from completing their syllabuses, disrupting the academic calendar and increasing the level of crimes in the country (Daily post, and 2011).

There is this general belief that education contributes substantially to the growth and development of a country. But when it comes to a situation where the government of a country is not interested in what is happening in the academic sector so as to improve them to meet up with the standard of other countries, then it calls for questioning.

According to Kagbaranen (2012) in Amadi and Urho (2015), any government that does not encourage the youths to educate has directly compromised the future of the nation, and such a government is not worth living. Today, the quality of education offered by higher educational institutions in Nigeria has deteriorated substantially (Mohammed and Gbenu 2007 in Amdi and Urho 2015). This deterioration or incessant closures is due to strike actions, and the effect of these repeated closures of university and academic programs has posed a lot of negative effects on the nation which can be better imagined than describe.

Recently, the government announced they cannot sign what they will not be able to implement with ASUU and created a new union call CONUA to replace them threatening to dissolve ASUU as a union. It is quite obvious to see that in a situation that all hands should be at deck to ensure that the strike action that has been lingering for too long is brought to an end, the federal government is yet to take serious steps in order to meet the demands of the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU). The nation's academic sector has suffered setbacks as a result of this incessant strikes and has led paved way to uncontrollable crime rate, unwanted pregnancies and untimely death of both the students and the lecturers who may not have been able to take care of themselves medically as a result of the stoppage of their salaries by the government all in the name of "no work, no pay".

Presently in Nigerian, it is no longer a story that lecturers are dying on daily basis. But it is surprising that at 62 anniversary celebration of Nigeria as a country of being independent from British rule, the educational sector is nothing to write home. A question can also arise, where are we heading to as a country when being faced with all these predicaments?

THE NECESSITY FOR RETHINKING

There is every tendency that ASUU strike actions will continue to have negative impacts on the students, lecturers and the entire society. As such, there is need for a rethink by the government on the possible ways of putting an end to the menace. The negligence of government on the educational sector has caused the system to lose its value to a high extent, thereby killing the interest of the learners. The general slangs and believes today is that, education is not for everyone. This has caused some youths, who should be aiming at going to school and studying, to drop out of school, joining secret cults and ending up being nuisance in the society.

As previously asked, where are we headed as a country when being faced with all these predicaments? This question alone should serve as a call for a rethink and immediate action. The system needs to be revitalized with the needed resources, it should be returned to its position, given the necessary supports. Payment of salaries should be at due season, infrastructure should be put in place in order to enhance effective teaching and process, parents should be given that hope again of having children who will come and take over from them.

The economy of the nation needs to be reshaped. This will help create avenues for availability of employment for the youths. It will reduce the high rate of poverty, crime and also reduce the rate of death among lecturers and students. Government

should have a rethink of coming to the negotiation table for a peaceful dialogue with Academic Union of Universities (ASUU), options should be suggested and agreement should met on how to restore the lost glory of the educational system and also the improvement of global best practices in the country. Working conditions of the lecturers should be looked into by providing the needed fund which will serve as a boost to enhance effectiveness in the teaching and learning process, thereby yielding good result at the end.

Conclusion

The incessant strike action has become a problem that has lingered for so long in the country, and yet nothing serious has been done. Strike has made the planning for universities academic activities to be very difficult. The re-planning, re-preparing the school calendar, reassigning old tasks to new staff and no achieving of certain long term goals due to the prolonged accomplishment are all results of strike actions.

Strike action is an event that consumes and waste a lot of time which implies that urgent attention is needed to solve this problem. It is an ill-wind that blows no one any good. The students, lecturers, and indeed the society as a whole have in one way or the other had their share of the negative implications. In all the strike actions, students are the most affected because the academic programs will be extended to their detriment. This has resulted to crimes within the institution and in the society at large.

The constant strike actions in the educational system has led to a low quality education as lecturers' outputs are low. There is instability in the development of educational sector and has given rise to the falling standard of education in Nigeria. There is need to revitalize the educational sector of the country and this can be done through the reaching and signing of the agreement made by the federal government to the Academic Staff Union of Universities.

Recommendations

The adoption and utilization of the recommendations below to industrial strike will rapidly promote the industrial harmony and also initiate a reliable declining rate of strike actions desired for the development of Nigeria as a nation.

1. Government should improve the welfare and condition of lecturers by providing them with adequate infrastructural facilities in their working environment.
2. Funds should be provided adequately in order to encourage effective research.
3. The existing educational laws should be renewed to make it more flexible in order to match with the present day reality.

4. Government should intervene immediately when issues of strike arise so as to reduce frequency of strike actions.
5. Employers/employees' interpersonal relations should be enhanced and constructive communication process developed. This will help prevent incessant strike actions.
6. Stakeholders should act as intermediaries when issues of strike arise as to bring lasting solutions that will improve educational sector and not taking sides.
7. Union should not encourage strike action, but rather, they should encourage negotiation to resolve issues of development.

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